

Site: SPHINX TEMPLE Season GS 79-80

Area: N. COLONNADE Square R16 Locus Number (4c)

Progress of Excavation 27/I/80 R16 A1: Surface (4c) fairly level.

Show concentration small-mid. limestone frags. Couple carbon spots, sm. small granite frags. Cleared w/ trowel tip action and brush. Concentration of heavy limestone pieces close to surface (4d). This cleaned, photod, planned 1:10. Question: would any arbitrary level in (4) or (4c) or (4d) give this concentration of limestone if each stone in fill so individually cleaned? STONES lifted.

(4d) Remained to expose surface (4d) 2/II/80: Surface of (4c) shows larger to mid. limestone frags, smaller granite frags, stone rubble; R16 A2 cleared down bit →

Locus Description "BROWN SAND WITH STONE RUBBLE

Location in Square See PLAN

Under Locus (4b) BUFF CLAY-GYPSUM Over Locus (4d) 8.10-8.16

Locus Dimensions _____

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials Much Granite, Polerite, Alabaster

Frag. More pottery than other loci including some w/ burnished red wash and one indicating S although only body frag of inflection.

No rims or bases. At least 1 seeped-like impression* (photod macro and dry husk(?)). Small Charcoal Frags throughout. Mud spots between stones.

lower than R16A, which is planned at bottom of (4b)-(4c) meeting. // (4c)
taken down to level of large limestone pieces. 1:10 plan of stones
from R16A, continued to S.T. N. wall. IN NE corner trench, at E
Balk and against bedrock foundation ledge, is largest limestone
piece so far removed, approx. 35 x 20 cm. Fill removed contained
mud spot, granite, dolerite, alabaster chips, some ND CRW sherds,
carbon flecks. LIMESTONE material after sifting - large to very fine w.
small chips alabaster, granite. Some small bone frags, carbon,
mud spots under large stone level.